

Preparing Ultrasound Imaging Data for Artificial Intelligence Tasks: Anonymisation, Cropping, and Tagging

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Keywords: Ultrasound Imaging, DICOM, Anonymisation, Cropping, Tagging, Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Abstract: Ultrasound imaging is a widely used diagnostic method in various clinical contexts, requiring efficient and accurate data preparation workflows for artificial intelligence (AI) tasks. Preparing ultrasound data presents challenges such as ensuring data privacy, extracting diagnostically relevant regions, and associating contextual metadata. This paper introduces a standalone application designed to streamline the preparation of ultrasound DICOM files for AI applications across different medical use cases. The application facilitates three key processes: (1) anonymisation, ensuring compliance with privacy standards by removing sensitive metadata; (2) cropping, isolating relevant regions in images or video frames to enhance the utility for AI analysis; and (3) tagging, enriching files with additional metadata such as anatomical position and imaging purpose. Built with an intuitive interface and robust backend, the application optimises DICOM file processing for efficient integration into AI workflows. The effectiveness of the tool is evaluated using a dataset of Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT) ultrasound images, demonstrating significant improvements in data preparation efficiency. This work establishes a generalizable framework for ultrasound imaging data preparation while offering specific insights into DVT-focused AI workflows. Future work will focus on further automation and expanding support to additional imaging modalities as well as evaluating the tool in a clinical setting.

1 INTRODUCTION

Machine learning (ML) has already achieved significant breakthroughs in medicine, especially in the automated diagnosis in medical imaging, automated management of administrative tasks, and exploration of the structure of bio-molecules, particularly proteins (Habehh and Gohel, 2021). A critical prerequisite for the successful application of machine learning in medical imaging is the preparation of high-quality, labelled datasets. This process, often referred to as ML training data preparation, is particularly intricate due to several factors: the need for strict anonymisation to ensure patient privacy, the identification and extraction of diagnostically relevant image regions, and the association of contextual metadata, such as anatomical position and purpose. Ensuring patient privacy through anonymisation is especially critical, as it supports both ethical considerations and compliance with data protection regulations in medical research.

Medical imaging and signal data management is almost exclusively based on the DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communication On Medicine) image and communication standard (ISO 12052, 2017). DICOM supports all medical imaging modalities but also organises data into two key components: (1) the *metadata*, which include patient-specific information (e.g., name, date of birth, and hospital details), as well as examination-specific data (e.g., modality type, acquisition parameters), and (2) the *imaging data*, which consist of pixel-based representations of the medical image or video. In addition, some metadata fields may be “burnt-in” directly onto the imaging data, as is common in ultrasound imaging, further complicating the anonymisation process.

Traditional approaches to DICOM data preparation for ML training, including the removal or obfuscation of sensitive metadata and annotations from both the header and the image itself, are often manual and time-intensive. These limitations hinder the scalability of AI-based solutions in clinical practice, underlining the importance of automated tools that can handle both anonymisation and efficient dataset preparation. This involves ensuring data privacy, standardising formats, isolating relevant image regions,

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and enriching the data with metadata to meet the quality requirements for ML training.

Ultrasound imaging, as a widely used modality in clinical practice, exemplifies these challenges due to its operator-dependent variability and its application across diverse diagnostic contexts. While these issues are common across ultrasound imaging use cases, they become particularly critical in specific conditions such as deep vein thrombosis (DVT). DVT is a serious medical condition characterised by the formation of blood clots within deep veins, most commonly in the lower extremities (Waheed et al., 2024). Ultrasound imaging is the primary diagnostic modality for DVT due to its non-invasive nature and real-time imaging capabilities. However, the complexity of analysing ultrasound data, coupled with variability in operator technique and patient anatomy, poses challenges for consistent and accurate diagnosis (Baker et al., 2024). Artificial intelligence (AI) offers a promising approach to addressing these challenges, automating tasks such as vessel segmentation and thrombus detection (Maiti and Arunachalam, 2022).

This paper introduces a tool, called US-DICOMizer, to automate and streamline the preparation of ultrasound DICOM files for AI-based workflows. While the tool is designed for general ultrasound imaging applications, it is evaluated using a dataset of DVT ultrasound exams as a test case. The application incorporates three key functionalities: (1) anonymisation to remove sensitive patient information while preserving essential metadata for AI tasks, (2) cropping to extract relevant regions from images or videos, and (3) tagging to annotate files with critical metadata, such as anatomical position, imaging purpose, and other contextual information. These functionalities aim to address the unique requirements of ultrasound imaging data preparation while ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations and clinical standards.

This work is part of the ThrombUS+ project, co-funded by the European Union (EU) under Grant Agreement No. 101137227 (Kaldoudi et al., 2024). The ThrombUS+ initiative aims to develop an innovative, operator-independent wearable diagnostic device designed to facilitate the early detection and diagnosis of DVT using various diagnostic data modalities, including ultrasound imaging. As part of this initiative, the US-DICOMizer application addresses critical data preparation needs for AI-based workflows in DVT and other ultrasound imaging applications.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of related work in DICOM data preparation and AI in ultrasound imaging. Section 3 details the methodology and design of the application, including its anonymisation, cropping, and tagging functionalities. Section 4

discusses the technical implementation details, highlighting the tools and frameworks employed. Section 5 presents results demonstrating the performance and the user experience of the application. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper by summarising the contributions of this work to AI-based medical imaging and provides future directions.

2 RELATED WORK

The preparation of ultrasound imaging data for artificial intelligence (AI) tasks requires specialised tools to address the unique challenges of this modality. Anonymisation, cropping, and tagging are critical steps to ensure patient privacy, enhance data utility, and facilitate effective data sharing. Existing solutions have focused on general medical imaging or specific modalities, often neglecting the particular requirements of ultrasound imaging for tasks like vessel segmentation and thrombus detection. This section reviews related work on anonymisation, cropping, and tagging techniques in medical imaging, highlighting their relevance and limitations in the context of ultrasound.

Numerous anonymisation tools have been developed to safeguard patient privacy while ensuring compliance with DICOM (Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine) standards. Monteiro et al. (2017) introduced a de-identification pipeline leveraging convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for character recognition, achieving an anonymisation rate of 89.2%. Similarly, Rodríguez González et al. (2010) developed an open-source toolkit for DICOM data de-identification tailored to multicenter trials, offering customisation based on specific privacy needs. However, these tools are primarily designed for neuroimaging and lacked features specific to ultrasound workflows. Haselgrove et al. (2014b) presented a system for anonymising DICOM data in neuroimaging research, ensuring compliance with quality control standards but leaving the unique needs of ultrasound imaging unaddressed.

Cropping and tagging techniques play a crucial role in isolating diagnostically relevant regions, anonymising burned-in annotations text, and associating metadata with medical images. Interactive anonymisation tools, such as the Cornell Anonymisation Toolkit (Xiao et al., 2009), allow users to manually crop and anonymise datasets but do not offer automation or optimisation for ultrasound imaging. Tools like DICOM Anonymiser and dicom-anon4 support tagging within the framework of DICOM standards (Haselgrove et al., 2014a), but their focus on neuroimaging limits their relevance to ultrasound-specific needs. More recently, image cropping techniques based on grid-anchor formulations have

emerged in general computer vision (e.g., CNN-based methods), but these approaches are designed for aesthetic image processing rather than clinical applications (Zeng et al., 2022).

Despite these advancements, significant gaps remain in addressing the specific requirements of ultrasound imaging. Existing tools are often modality-specific and fail to provide comprehensive solutions that integrate anonymisation, cropping, and tagging for ultrasound data. Furthermore, inconsistent standards across imaging communities pose challenges to the adoption of unified workflows. This paper addresses these challenges by introducing a tool, as a standalone application, tailored to the preparation of ultrasound DICOM data for AI tasks. While the tool is designed to be broadly applicable across ultrasound imaging use cases, its functionality is evaluated using deep vein thrombosis (DVT) examinations as a test case to validate its performance and utility.

3 METHODOLOGY

The development of US-DICOMizer is driven by the broader requirements of ultrasound imaging data preparation for artificial intelligence (AI) tasks, while incorporating insights from the ThrombUS+ project (Kaldoudi et al., 2024). As part of this initiative, Clinical Study A (Drougka, 2024), described in detail in the data collection manual available at <https://app.thrombus.eu/studies/a/>, is used to validate its functionality. The methodology combines insights from established imaging protocols with tailored tool development to streamline key data preparation steps, such as anonymisation, cropping, and tagging. It excludes the labelling and annotation of the collected images and videos, which will be performed as a separate and necessary step for AI training.

Requirements and Design Principles. Clinical Study A outlines a structured process for ultrasound data collection, emphasising accurate imaging of specific anatomical sites, tagging critical metadata, and ensuring privacy compliance. This process inspired the design of US-DICOMizer, following a user-centred approach which automates data preparation to reduce manual effort while preserving the integrity and diagnostic value of the images and videos. The tool adheres to the following principles:

1. **Data Privacy Compliance:** Adherence to anonymisation standards, ensuring compatibility with HIPAA and GDPR.
2. **Standardisation and Consistency:** Integration of tagging functionalities aligned with DICOM standards to support AI-based downstream tasks.
3. **Workflow Efficiency:** Minimising manual inter-

vention while enabling flexibility through interactive features.

4. **Automation and Scalability:** Streamlining repetitive tasks such as cropping and anonymisation to improve efficiency across large datasets.
5. **Clinical Relevance:** Supporting tagging based on the anatomical positions and diagnostic context detailed in the Clinical Study A protocol.

Data Collection Context. In Clinical Study A, healthcare professionals collect ultrasound images and videos following a structured protocol to assess key venous sites in the lower extremities. The imaging included:

- *Compression Ultrasound:* Capturing frames and videos to evaluate vein compressibility at specific sites (e.g., common femoral vein, popliteal vein).
- *Color Doppler Ultrasound:* Enhancing diagnostic detail for specific anatomical regions.
- *Optional Imaging:* Capturing pathological sites (e.g., thrombus visualisation) where necessary.

US-DICOMizer integrates these requirements by providing a robust framework for importing, cropping, tagging, anonymizing, and exporting DICOM files, preserving the diagnostic and research value of the data.

Workflow. The workflow followed for preparing DICOM files with US-DICOMizer is presented in Figure 1 and involves the following key steps:

1. **File Loading and Validation:** Users can load single DICOM files, entire folders, or compressed archives. The tool validates the files to ensure compatibility and displays their metadata for review. Multiframe DICOMs are previewed frame-by-frame to facilitate inspection.
2. **Cropping and Tagging:**
 - **Cropping:** Users define relevant regions of interest either manually through an interactive GUI or by applying preset configurations. Multiframe cropping ensures uniformity across videos.
 - **Tagging:** Metadata, including anatomical position (e.g., proximal, distal), the side (left or right), and the image purpose, are applied to each file.
3. **Anonymisation:** Sensitive information is automatically removed or replaced, with user-defined configurations specifying which tags are to be deleted. The tool generates unique identifiers for studies, series, and instances to ensure compliance with data privacy regulations.
4. **Export:** Prepared DICOM files are exported as a ZIP archive, maintaining a standardised structure and ensuring compatibility with AI workflows.

Figure 1: US-DICOMizer workflow.

By aligning the application workflow with this protocol, US-DICOMizer bridges the gap between clinical imaging practices and AI-driven research, ensuring standardised, high-quality datasets.

4 IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

The development of the US-DICOMizer focuses on facilitating the preparation of ultrasound DICOM files for artificial intelligence (AI) tasks through an interactive and semi-automated workflow. The application is open-source and available on GitHub at <https://github.com/thrombusplus/US-DICOMizer>. Below, we outline the technical details of its design and implementation.

Development Environment and Frameworks. The application is implemented in Python, leveraging the following key libraries:

- **Tkinter:** For building a graphical user interface (GUI) to facilitate intuitive user interactions.
- **Pydicom:** For reading, editing, and anonymising DICOM files.
- **SimpleITK:** For image processing and visualisation of DICOM images.
- **Pillow (PIL):** For handling image formats and performing operations like cropping and saving.

- **NumPy:** For efficient array manipulations of image data.
- **Matplotlib:** For visualising images during processing.
- **Scikit-Image:** For advanced image manipulation and processing tasks.

Core Functionalities. Users can load individual DICOM files, entire folders, or ZIP archives containing multiple DICOM files. Imported files are displayed in a tree-view structure within the application, allowing users to preview metadata and image content. For multiframe DICOMs, a video slider facilitates frame-by-frame visualisation.

Cropping regions are defined interactively through the GUI or automatically based on pre-configured settings in the `settings.ini` file. These cropping parameters can be applied uniformly to all frames of multiframe DICOMs. Metadata tagging ensures the association of critical information, including anatomical position and image purpose, with each file. Crop settings are also saved to the configuration file for consistency across sessions.

Sensitive patient identifiers are removed or replaced during the anonymisation process. Attributes specified in the configuration file under the `[attributes_to_del]` section are deleted from each DICOM file. The application also generates new unique identifiers (UIDs) for the study, series, and instances to maintain data integrity while ensuring privacy compliance.

Processed DICOM files are exported as a compressed ZIP archive. The naming conventions and folder structure of the output are customisable via the application settings, ensuring compatibility with downstream workflows.

Error Handling and Logging. The application incorporates robust error handling to prevent workflow interruptions. For instance:

- Validation of DICOM files ensures that non-DICOM inputs are skipped during batch processing.
- Invalid or missing cropping parameters result in detailed error messages, guiding users to update their configuration files.
- A dedicated logging system records application activities and errors in a structured format for debugging and audit purposes.

Customisability. User-defined settings, such as cropping areas, compression levels, and attributes removal lists, are stored in an INI configuration file. This file allows for fine-grained control over the application's behaviour, enabling customisation to suit various use cases and device configurations.

(a) Loading of DICOM files.

(b) Selecting the appropriate DICOM files for anonymisation.

(c) Preview a DICOM file visually and as metadata.

Figure 2: Loading, selecting and previewing DICOM files.

Performance Optimisation. The application employs multithreading for tasks like previewing images and processing large datasets, ensuring smooth operation without GUI freezes. Efficient handling of image data through NumPy arrays and PIL ensures minimal processing time.

5 RESULTS

The proposed US-DICOMizer application is evaluated for its ability to streamline the preparation of ultrasound DICOM files for artificial intelligence (AI)

tasks through an intuitive sequence of steps: file loading and preview, cropping and tagging, anonymisation, and export. Below, we describe the workflow and outcomes achieved during testing.

Workflow Evaluation. Initially, users start the process by importing DICOM files through multiple options, including selecting individual files, importing entire folders, or uploading compressed archives (Figure 2.a). Imported files are displayed in the "Selected File" list, allowing users to preview images and inspect DICOM attributes, such as dimensions and metadata (Figure 2.c). Multiframe DICOM files include an interactive video slider for frame-by-frame

inspection. The interface provides users with the flexibility to reorder, remove, or review files before further processing (Figure 2.b).

Once files are selected, users define cropping regions to isolate diagnostically relevant portions of the image or video frames. Predefined cropping settings are automatically applied where applicable, with the option for manual adjustment using an interactive preview tool (Figure 3.a). Cropping parameters could be applied uniformly across all frames or adjusted for individual files, ensuring consistency and relevance in data preparation. Additionally, cropping parameters are saved to a configuration file, allowing users to replicate consistent settings across multiple sessions (Figure 3.b). Concurrently, users add tags to each file to specify anatomical position (e.g., femoral vein (FV) or popliteal vein (PV)), side (e.g., left or right leg), and image purpose (e.g., diagnostic or non-diagnostic quality) (Figure 3.c). These tags ensure the association of critical metadata with the prepared files, enhancing their utility for downstream AI tasks.

(a) Process of image cropping.

(b) Save cropping area in settings. (c) Select tag.

Figure 3: Cropping and tagging process.

With cropping and tagging completed, the

anonymisation process is initiated (Figure 4). The application removes sensitive patient identifiers while preserving essential metadata for AI processing. Files with correctly defined cropping areas and tags are visually marked to indicate readiness for anonymisation. Validation checks prevented the anonymisation of incomplete or improperly prepared files, maintaining data integrity.

Anonymised DICOM files are exported as a compressed ZIP archive for convenient sharing and storage (Figure 5). Users specify the destination folder for the exported archive, completing the preparation process. This final step ensures that the files are ready for integration into AI workflows with minimal manual intervention.

Performance and User Experience. The application demonstrates high efficiency and ease of use. On average, ultrasound exams comprising 15-30 DICOM files (including single-frame and multiframe) are fully prepared (including loading, cropping, tagging, anonymisation, and export) within 3-6 minutes. Exporting to a ZIP archive required less than 1-2 seconds for exams of similar size.

The anonymisation process was evaluated for its average execution times per frame across various photometric interpretations and cropping areas, as shown in Table 1. For single-frame ultrasound images with a resolution of 1200x800 pixels, Monochrome2 photometric interpretation required 19-23 milliseconds, depending on the cropping area. In contrast, the YBR_FULL_422 and RGB interpretations took longer, with times ranging from 25-30 milliseconds and 49-61 milliseconds, respectively. For ultrasound multiframe DICOMs, the processing

Table 1: Average execution times (per frame) of anonymisation process for various photometric interpretations and cropping areas.

Media Type (resolution)	Photometric Interpretation	Cropping Area (pixels)	AVG Time per Frame (msec)
Ultrasound Image (1200x800) [100 runs]	Monochrome2	576x432	19
		768x576	21
		1024x768	23
	YBR_FULL_422	576x432	25
		768x576	27
		1024x768	30
RGB	576x432	49	
	768x576	53	
	1024x768	61	
Ultrasound Multi-frame (1200x800) [10 runs]	Monochrome2	576x432	102
		768x576	105
		1024x768	108
	YBR_FULL_422	576x432	117
		768x576	119
		1024x768	124
RGB	576x432	241	
	768x576	244	
	1024x768	250	

Figure 4: Start the anonymisation process after properly cropping and tagging the required DICOM files.

Figure 5: Export anonymised DICOM files as a ZIP file.

times increased as expected: Monochrome2 required 102–108 milliseconds per frame, YBR_FULL_422 required 117–124 milliseconds, and RGB interpretation ranged from 241–250 milliseconds per frame.

These results were produced using ultrasound exams from eight different ultrasound medical devices manufactured by four vendors, and calculated on a laptop computer running Windows 10, with an Intel Core i7-7700HQ CPU at 2.8 GHz and 16 GB of RAM. While DVT datasets were used for testing, the tool is designed for broader ultrasound imaging use cases. Conclusively, this experiment highlights that performance trade-offs are associated with both photometric complexity and cropping dimensions.

User feedback emphasises the application's intuitive interface and streamlined workflow. Key features, such as interactive previews before and after

anonymisation as well as cropping and tagging tools, contribute to user satisfaction. Keyboard shortcuts for common tasks further enhanced efficiency, making the application a practical tool for medical imaging professionals.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The development and evaluation of US-DICOMizer underscore its effectiveness in streamlining the preparation of ultrasound DICOM files for artificial intelligence (AI) tasks. By automating key processes such as anonymisation, cropping, and tagging, the application addresses critical challenges in ultrasound data preparation, including compliance with privacy standards, relevance of imaging regions, and metadata contextualisation. The integration of these functionalities into an intuitive, open-source platform facilitates scalable, standardised workflows for various ultrasound imaging AI applications. While the tool was validated using deep vein thrombosis (DVT) datasets, its design and functionality are adaptable to a wide range of clinical use cases.

Preliminary results demonstrate that US-DICOMizer significantly reduces manual effort and enhances the consistency of prepared datasets, enabling faster and more reliable AI model training. The alignment of the tool's design with the structured protocol of Clinical Study A from the ThrombUS+ project ensures its clinical relevance and applicability. Furthermore, its adaptability to various imaging

workflows and compliance with industry standards position it as a versatile tool for medical imaging research.

Despite these achievements, several opportunities for future development remain. First, expanding the tool's support to additional imaging modalities, such as computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), could broaden its utility. Second, incorporating advanced AI algorithms directly into the tool could enable automated cropping and tagging based on learned patterns, further reducing the need for manual input. Third, large-scale validation of the tool in clinical settings is necessary to evaluate its robustness and user satisfaction across diverse environments and datasets. Lastly, integrating real-time feedback mechanisms and interoperability with eCRF (electronic case report form) platforms could streamline data sharing, automate the collection process and ensure compliance with clinical trial regulations.

In conclusion, US-DICOMizer represents a significant step toward automating and standardising ultrasound data preparation for AI-driven healthcare solutions. With planned enhancements and broader adoption, it has the potential to accelerate advancements in diagnostic imaging and personalised medicine, supporting a wide range of clinical and research applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is co-funded by the European Union, under the Horizon Europe Innovation Action ThrombUS+ (Grant Agreement No. 101137227). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or HADEA as the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority HADEA can be held responsible for them. Also, this work was carried out in the context of the Inter-Institutional Master's Program "Biomedical Informatics" with the support of the School of Medicine, Democritus University of Thrace and the Athena Research Center in Greece.

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